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Household Transmission Investigation (HHTI) & Associated Risk Factors for Influenza A, Influenza B and Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) infection amongst Residents of Delhi, India.

**This protocol is aligned with the WHO Unity protocol on Closed Setting Transmission
Investigation for Respiratory Pathogens with Pandemic Potential**

List of Abbreviations:

CONWISE	Consortium for the Standardization of Influenza Seroepidemiology
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
FFX	First Few X
GIP	Global Influenza Programme
GOARN	Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network
HAHC	Hakim Abdul Hamid Centenary
HAI	Hospital associated Infections
HCW	Hospital Infection Control Committee
HHTI	Household Transmission Investigation
HIMSR	Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences & Research
ICMR	Indian Council of Medical Research
IEC	Institutional Ethical Committee
IPC	Infection Prevention Control
MoHFW	Ministry of Health & Family Welfare
OPD	Out Patient Department
HHTI	Household Transmission Investigation
IHR	International Health Regulations
IPSS	Influenza Pandemic Special Investigations and Studies
IQR	Interquartile Range
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
R	Basic reproductive number
Reff	Effective reproductive number
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RSV	Respiratory Syncytial Virus
SAR	Secondary Attack Rate
SARI	Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SARS-CoV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
SCAR	Secondary Clinical Attack Rate
WHE	Health Emergencies Programme
WHO	World Health Organization

Household Transmission Investigation (HTTI) & Associated Risk Factors for Pandemic Influenza A, Influenza B and Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) infection amongst Residents of Delhi, India.

1.1 Background to Pandemic Investigations and Studies

Influenza is a serious global health threat that impacts all countries: every year, there are an estimated 1 billion cases, 3-5 million severe cases, and 290,000-650,000 influenza-related respiratory deaths worldwide (3, 4). Influenza viruses are constantly changing and major changes, occurring through antigenic shift, can result in novel influenza viruses. When a novel influenza virus emerges against which people have little or no immunity, they have the potential to cause a pandemic (5). The most recent influenza pandemic occurred in 2009, caused by a novel influenza A(H1N1) virus. This pandemic caused substantial global morbidity and mortality and the virus continues to circulate as a seasonal virus (6).

Influenza B poses a considerable public health burden in the WHO South-East Asia Region (SEAR), accounting for up to 50% of laboratory-confirmed influenza cases in peak years. In India, recent national surveillance reported that during the 2021 monsoon season, influenza B/Victoria was the dominant strain, while the 2023 winter saw another spike in influenza B cases among children, who remain especially vulnerable to severe outcomes. Data from a pan-India surveillance study enrolling over 34,000 patients between July 2021 and October 2022 revealed that influenza B, particularly the B/Victoria lineage, was prevalent during the high transmission season, leading to significant pediatric hospitalizations. Regional studies echo these findings, with hospital-based surveillance in Southern and Eastern India reporting the highest influenza B incidence among preschoolers and school-age children, occasionally resulting in acute respiratory distress and sporadic mortality. Despite these trends, comprehensive estimates of influenza B-associated mortality are lacking, highlighting the urgent need for strengthened nationwide surveillance and targeted vaccination policies in India.

Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) is a leading cause of severe acute respiratory infections among children under five in the WHO South-East Asia Region, with India carrying a significant burden. Surveillance data consistently identify RSV as the primary viral cause of hospitalization for lower respiratory tract infections in this age group. In northern India, RSV accounts for up to 16% of pediatric hospitalizations, with infants under six months facing hospitalization rates as high as 15.2 per 1,000. Studies confirm high RSV prevalence among infants, especially of the RSV-B genotype, with persistent circulation throughout the year. The burden of RSV extends beyond hospitalisation. Children often experience prolonged symptoms and are at increased risk of recurrent respiratory problems. The impact on families is substantial—up to 42% of parents report serious quality-of-life disruptions, including anxiety, sleep loss, and work absenteeism. This corresponds to a median utility loss of 0.14 and measurable declines in QALYs.

These findings highlight the urgent need for improved RSV surveillance, early diagnostics, and equitable access to preventive tools like maternal vaccines and monoclonal antibodies. Strengthening caregiver support and long-term follow-up is equally essential. A coordinated national strategy is critical to reduce the clinical and social impact of RSV on Indian children and families.

Following a review of the global response to the last influenza pandemic (2009 influenza pandemic H1N1) (7), the global Consortium for the Standardization of Influenza Seroepidemiology (CONSISE) (8), and World Health Organization's (WHO) Influenza Pandemic Special Investigations and Studies initiative were established to develop a suite of standardized early investigation protocols, supported by the Global Influenza Programme (9) and the Pandemic Influenza Preparedness (PIP) Framework (10). Standardized protocols were also implemented following the emergence of Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) in 2012 (11), and Zika virus in 2016 (12).

In January 2020, the novel coronavirus, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), responsible for the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) was declared a public health emergency of international concern by the WHO. This required rapid implementation of early investigations to inform appropriate national and global public health actions. Adaptation of existing protocols was initiated from the first weeks of the detection of the novel coronavirus and further developed under the WHO initiative, Unity Studies (2). The Unity Studies protocols standardized methods and facilitated rapid generation of local data for public health action and comparison of key epidemiological parameters across regions and globally (2, 13-15). Based on the learning of the COVID-19 response, a series of standardized template protocols have been developed for both disease specific investigations such as influenza and for any novel respiratory virus of pandemic potential for the implementation of standardized and quality investigations and studies to ensure readiness in advance of a future pandemic. These have been developed as part of the WHO Investigations and Studies, Unity Studies initiative. The initiative aims to provide an 'at the ready' international framework for preparedness and response to future pandemics, providing a suite of enhanced surveillance and operational research activities that are harmonized to help provide detailed insight into the epidemiological characteristics of emerging or re-emerging respiratory pathogens of pandemic potential. They are included in both the Global Influenza Strategy (16) (pillar 6: "Number of sites (or geographical coverage) primed to conduct at least one of the WHO Pandemic Influenza Special Investigations in case of a pandemic with target for 2023: "At least 2 operationally ready sites in each WHO region (so 12 sites)") and the third version of the High-Level Implementation. Investigations and Studies are also included in the Mosaic Respiratory Surveillance Framework (17).

1.2 Introduction to Closed Setting Transmission Investigations and their approach

The detection and spread of new pandemic influenza viruses are characterized by real uncertainty over the key epidemiological, clinical and virological characteristics of this novel virus and particularly its ability to spread in the human population and its virulence (case-severity) (18). The household provides a strategic setting to track influenza infections among close contacts of cases because the denominator can be well-defined, the extent of exposure is similar and follow-up of household contacts is generally more feasible than in an undefined setting (19). As such it is important to monitor transmission in households, where up to 30% of influenza virus transmission is believed to occur (20, 21). Such studies allow us to determine transmission dynamics (reproduction number and serial interval) of the virus as well as to understand the clinical spectrum of illness in secondary cases (19, 20).

A substantial fraction of influenza virus infections may be associated with mild disease that does not require medical attention and may include asymptomatic infection (19). Infections identified in household contacts may potentially be

generalizable to naturally-acquired pandemic influenza virus infections (in contrast to for example only cases presenting for emergency care among which there would be fewer mild cases). Following household contacts with similar levels of exposure to infection from primary cases can also permit identification of the asymptomatic fraction (19, 20).

More generally, follow-up and testing of respiratory specimens and serum of household contacts can provide useful information about newly identified cases, as well as the spectrum of illness and frequency (by for example age) of asymptomatic and symptomatic influenza. Household transmission studies also provide the opportunity to understand the natural history of infection, including the pattern of symptom development, antibody kinetics, and viral kinetics. Higher titers of antibodies against a specific influenza strain correlate with protection against infection by that strain (21). Humoral antibody titers tend to rise following influenza virus infection and remain elevated for a prolonged period, therefore, surveillance of antibody seroprevalence in a population can permit inference about the cumulative incidence of infection in that population (22). Inferences based on seroprevalence are simpler for pandemic viruses where initial seroprevalence is very low due to the virus being novel in origin. The characteristics of rises in antibody titer following influenza virus infection can vary by strain and method of ascertainment (23)

Studies in households allow determination of the transmission dynamics (reproduction number and serial interval) of the virus, as well as aiding understanding of the clinical spectrum of illness in secondary cases.^[2] Households settings are also useful to observe chains of transmission in an epidemic, as the pool of susceptible, exposed individuals is larger. Therefore, in the case of multiple waves of infection through the closed setting, unique insight into transmission dynamics can be derived in the early epidemic stages.

Initial surveillance has focused primarily on patients with severe disease, and, as such, the full spectrum of the disease, including the extent and fraction of mild or asymptomatic infection that does not require medical attention, is not clear. Infections identified in households and close contacts are potentially generalizable to naturally acquired infections (in contrast to cases presenting for emergency care, among which there would be fewer mild cases). Following close contacts with similar levels of exposure to infection from primary cases can also permit identification of the asymptomatic fraction. Principally, follow-up and testing of respiratory specimens and serum of close contacts can provide useful information about newly identified cases, as well as the spectrum of illness and frequency (by, for example, age) of asymptomatic and symptomatic infection.

The following protocol has been designed to investigate households setting transmission of the influenza virus as a part of UNITY Studies. Each country may tailor some aspects of this protocol to align with public health, laboratory and clinical systems, according to their country capacity and availability of resources, as well as the cultural appropriateness of the protocol. However, by using a standardized protocol such as the one described here, epidemiological exposure data and biological samples can be systematically collected and shared rapidly in a format that can be easily aggregated, tabulated and analyzed across many different settings globally. This will facilitate timely estimates of the severity and transmissibility of influenza virus infection, as well as informing public health responses and policy decisions. This is particularly important in the context of a novel respiratory pathogen.

New Delhi, India Scenario

Delhi is divided into 11 districts. The institute- Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (HIMSR) and Hakim Abdul Hamid Centenary(HAHC) hospital is a tertiary care institute with a recognized medical college and 800 bedded hospital and caters to patients from whole of Delhi and large footfall from South and South East district of Delhi.^[4] These districts have all sections of people from Higher socioeconomic class to lower socioeconomic class and the hospital sees a footfall form all sections.

We propose this study to be conducted amongst patients receiving care in HAH Centenary Hospital and their household contact for the better understanding of transmission of influenza virus amongst household settings. This study will be in partnership with WHO India.

2. OBJECTIVES

The overall aim of this protocol is to gain an understanding of the transmission dynamics among household contacts of laboratory-confirmed cases of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV respectively, as well as rapid and early information on key clinical, epidemiological and virological characteristics of them.

The primary objectives of this household settings transmission study are:

- **Transmissibility**
 - 1 . Secondary infection rate (SIR) of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection overall, and by key factors such as age and sex;
 2. Secondary clinical attack rate (SCAR) as a proxy measure of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection among household contacts, overall, and by key factors such as age and sex;
- **Severity**
 - Clinical presentation of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection and the course of the disease.
 - Symptomatic and asymptomatic proportions of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV cases.
 - Preliminary case- and infection-hospitalization and fatality ratios.

3. GLOSSARY AND DEFINITIONS

3.1 Glossary of Epidemiological Terms

- **Overall infection rate:** A measure of the total number of new infections of a pathogen among contacts of confirmed cases within a defined time period, determined by a positive laboratory result. This is assessed using methods like polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or serological assays on paired samples.
- **Overall clinical attack rate:** A measure of the total number of new symptomatic individuals among contacts in a defined time period. It acts as a proxy for the secondary infection rate (SIR) and depends on the clinical criteria used in case definitions.
- **Secondary infection rate (SIR):** A measure of the frequency of new infections of influenza influenza A/B RSV among contacts of confirmed cases in a defined time period, confirmed by a positive laboratory result. It is the rate at which contacts get infected, assessed by PCR or serological assays on paired samples.
- **Secondary clinical attack rate (SCAR):** A measure of the frequency of new symptomatic individuals among contacts in a defined time period. It is a proxy for the SIR and is dependent on the clinical criteria used for case definitions.
- **Asymptomatic proportion of cases:** The frequency of asymptomatic infections of influenza influenza A/B RSV among all confirmed cases in a defined time period. It represents the proportion of lab-confirmed cases who do not show symptoms of the disease.
- **Infection-hospitalization ratio:** The proportion of individuals with a laboratory-confirmed influenza influenza A/B RSV infection who are hospitalized for clinical management.
- **Infection-fatality ratio:** The proportion of individuals with a laboratory-confirmed influenza A/B RSV infection who die as a direct or indirect result of the infection.
- **Serial interval:** The time from the onset of symptoms in a primary case to the onset of symptoms in a secondary case.
- **Basic reproduction number (Ro):** The average number of infections produced by one infected individual during the early phase of an epidemic when almost all contacts are susceptible. This assumes little to no population-level immunity.
- **Effective reproduction number (Reff):** A measure of the transmission potential of a disease at a specific time (t), used after interventions are implemented or the number of susceptible individuals has decreased.
- **Incubation period:** The time between exposure that results in an infection and the start of the first clinical symptoms.
- **Duration of infectiousness:** The time during which a virus is shed and can be transmitted, regardless of whether clinical symptoms are present.
- **Generation interval:** The time from infection in a primary case to the infection of a secondary case.
- **Latent period:** The time between an individual being infected with and when they become infectious.
- **Duration of viral shedding:** The time for which the virus is shed, regardless of clinical symptoms

Figure 1: Relationship between time periods between primary case and a secondary case and main epidemiological parameters (Ref Islam et al. 2023)

This figure displays a timeline illustrating the key time intervals for disease transmission from a primary case to a secondary case.

- **For the Primary Case:** The timeline shows the point of infection, the start of symptoms, and the point at which the secondary case is infected.
 - **Incubation Period:** The time from infection to the onset of symptoms.
 - **Latent Period:** The time from infection to becoming infectious.
 - **Generation Interval:** The time from infection of the primary case to the infection of the secondary case.
 - **Serial Interval:** The time from the onset of symptoms in the primary case to the onset of symptoms in the secondary case.
- **For the Secondary Case:** The timeline shows the point of infection and the subsequent onset of symptoms, with its own incubation period.

3.2 Definitions used in the household settings protocol

3.2.1 Case definitions

Box 1: Definition of a confirmed case in the household settings protocol

Confirmed case:

- **A person with laboratory confirmation either of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection, irrespective of clinical signs and symptoms. Laboratory confirmation includes receiving a positive result from polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or virus isolation.**

- **ILI Case definition:** Acute respiratory infection with measured fever of $\geq 38\text{ C}^\circ$ and cough with onset within the last 10 days.
 - **Category A:** Mild fever and cough/ sore throat with or without body ache, headache, diarrhoea, vomiting.
 - **Category B:** High-grade fever, severe sore throat with or without body ache, headache, diarrhoea, vomiting. Or one or more high risk condition such as: Age ≥ 65 years, Pregnancy (including up to two weeks post-partum), Infants and Children aged ≤ 5 years (especially <2 years of age), Chronic respiratory disease, Chronic heart, kidney, liver or neurological disease, Diabetes mellitus, Blood disorders (including haemoglobinopathies), Persons with immunosuppression (including HIV/ AIDS & use of long-term (≥ 2 weeks) corticosteroids, Post-transplant patients), Extreme obesity (BMI $\geq 40\text{ kg/m}^2$), Malignancy
 - **Category C:** Category A and Category B patients with one or more following signs and symptoms:

Symptoms	Signs
• Breathlessness	• Tachypnoea
• Hemoptysis	• SPO2 <92
• Altered mental status	• Hypotension
• Somnolence and Poor feeding (in children)	• Reduced urine output
• Seizures	• Cyanosis
• Decreased urine output	
• Persistence or worsening of initial symptoms beyond 72 hours	
• Worsening of underlying chronic conditions like Diabetes Mellitus, Chronic Kidney Disease	

- **SARI Case definition:** An acute respiratory infection with history of fever or measured fever of $\geq 38\text{ C}^\circ$ and cough with onset within the last 10 days and requires hospitalization.

3.2.2 Household and household contact definitions

HHTIs investigations focus on household contacts, which are a subset of the total number of close contacts associated with some sphere of activity of case within a household. The definitions are proposed in Box 2

Box 2: Household and household contact definitions

Household definition: A household is defined as a group of people (2 or more) living in the same residence. In practice, the technical definition may vary due to social, political and cultural practices (25). For operationality, in this study we consider these as **Household**

- **Two or more people living together in a domestic residence (residential institutions, such as boarding schools, dormitories, hostels or prisons will be excluded).**
- **A dwelling or group of dwellings with a shared kitchen or common opening onto a shared household space.**

Household contact definition: A household contact is defined as any person who resides or resided in the same household as the Confirmed case either of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection

A household contact may be:

- **A person who commonly resides in the same household as the case**
- **Any person who had resided in the same household as the case for at least one night during the exposure period (two days before to 10 days after onset of illness in the index case)**

3.3 Classification of HHTI participants

During the investigation, transmission events will be observed through laboratory testing and symptom monitoring of close contacts. These observations help identify transmission chains and classify all participants as described in Box 3.

Box 3: Classification of closed setting participants

- **A. Index case:** the first laboratory confirmed case of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV reported or identified within a cluster. It is the identification of the index case that leads to recruitment into the study.
- **B. Primary case:** an individual who has a laboratory confirmed influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection and has the first evidence of infection within the recruited cluster (i.e., has the earliest symptom onset date or positive laboratory test). Subsequent cases are secondary, tertiary etc.
- **C. Co-primary case(s):** cases with onset dates less than 24 hours from the onset date of the primary case are considered to be “co-primary” cases. If the primary case does not have an onset date, only a date of initial laboratory confirmation of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection, then it is not possible to determine if a contact is a co-primary case.
- **D. Imported case:** an index, primary or co-primary case with a history of travel from an affected area in the 14 days before disease onset.
- **E. Secondary cases:** Close contacts with:
Laboratory confirmed influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection detected between 24 hours to 7 days after the latest positive laboratory test date of the primary and/or co-primary case of same pathogen,

NOTE: It is important to consider the timing of exposure and virology of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV when classifying close contacts as secondary cases. Thorough testing protocols, symptom information and genomic sequencing data may help to distinguish between secondary cases and unrelated cases.

- **F. Suspected cases:** Suspected cases: are non-primary cases with fever (temperature $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$) AND [cough or shortness of breath or difficulty breathing], with a symptom onset date between 24 hours to 14 days after the latest positive laboratory test date of the primary and/or co-primary case.

NOTE: This definition only applies to cases identified after the primary case, i.e., when laboratory diagnostics are not available for secondary case classification.

- **G. Unrelated case:** includes other cases for the purposes of the HHTI investigation such as tertiary cases (those with evidence of being infected by a secondary case) and cases infected from other external sources (i.e., not the primary case)

4 MATERIAL AND METHODS

4.1 Study design

This HHTI investigation is a case-ascertained prospective household setting study of index cases of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV and household contacts, including infants and children, which may also be referred to as a “household transmission study” (19, 27, 28). Study participants and closed settings are identified from those with laboratory confirmed influenza infection.

This is distinct from a household cohort study in which a group of disease-free household are recruited and then followed over time. Case-ascertained transmission studies are more efficient than cohort studies when interest is in early estimation of the clinical, epidemiological and virological characteristics of the influenza A, Influenza B and RSV virus. This is because the risk of primary or secondary infection in a cohort would be expected to be low during the early stage of the pandemic before widespread community transmission was established. Closed setting transmission studies have also their limitations, as described in the literature (19, 27).

4.2 Study Setting

The study will be carried out in Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (HIMSR) and Hakim Abdul Hamid Centenary (HAHC) Hospital which is situated in South East Delhi. The HIMSR is a recognized medical college with about 1000 students currently enrolled, and the associated HAHC hospitals is a tertiary care institute with a 800 bedded hospital, caters to patients from whole of Delhi and large footfall from South and South East district of Delhi.^[4] Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, as a tertiary care hospital setting in South East Delhi, adheres to district surveillance guidelines and reports influenza cases daily under IHIP and monthly under HMIS. The institution also houses an epidemiological unit dedicated to outbreak investigations and management.

The details of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV positive patients will be collected from the institute’s lab on the same day of testing. The address and phone number will be noted and the team will visit the household on the same day for day 1 data and microbiological collection.

4.3 Population:

Study population: The population under investigation consists of the confirmed cases of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV and their close contacts in their households. As per HIMSR and HAHC hospital protocol, both Category B (high-risk) and Category C ILI patients are tested and treated. While current MoHFW guidelines recommend testing only for Category C patients, being a private institute, we also test high-risk Category B cases. Recruitment of index cases will be from the laboratory database of HIMSR & HAHC hospital in the pilot phase of the study; therefore, all laboratory-confirmed cases and their households will be eligible for inclusion in the study.

Households will be enrolled in the study once a confirmed influenza A, Influenza B and RSV case is identified in at least one member of the household. The detail of the case will be obtained from the institute’s lab and permission of the

state and district authority will be sought before beginning the study for further home visits and testing.

Households will be subsequently followed up to observe secondary infections on day 7,14 and 28. Every effort will be made to include all identified household contacts of cases of laboratory-confirmed influenza A, Influenza B and RSV.

4.4. Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

- households with a confirmed influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection identified.
- all contacts of the confirmed influenza A, Influenza B and RSV case residing in the same household;

Exclusion criteria

- Households will be excluded if:
 - the date of symptom onset of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV is the same for more than one family member (co-primary cases);
- **Hospitalized cases and their contacts** will be excluded from this study, as they have been removed from the household and therefore the level of exposure of household contacts is unclear. Hospitalized individuals may only represent a small subset of individuals in the community and are likely to be picked up in other clinical studies.

4.5 Data collection

Once an index case has been identified and recruited into the investigation, a study visit (if case is hospitalized due to severe illness/isolation purposes or isolating at home) or phone interview will need to be conducted to identify all household contacts for recruitment into the investigation.

A summary of the data and specimen collection forms can be found in [Table 1](#) and [Figure 2](#).

For cases, data will be collected using [Form A1](#) for the baseline visit (Day 1), followed by [Form A2](#) for the follow-up visit (day 7) to collect relevant sociodemographic and clinical information

For household contacts, data will be collected using [Form B1](#) for the baseline visit (day 1) followed by [Form B2](#) for the follow up visit (day 7) to collect relevant sociodemographic and clinical information.

[Form C](#) will be used for all specimen collection visits (throughout day 1 to day 7 for cases and household contacts).

[Form D](#) – Symptom diaries will be provided for all cases and household contacts to complete (throughout day 2 to day 14), to record presence or absence of various signs or symptoms. A proxy may fill out the symptom diaries on behalf of those unable to complete the form themselves. Note that symptoms are recorded on day 1 as part of the baseline form ([Form A1](#) or [Form B1](#))

Household contacts found to be positive with influenza A, Influenza B and RSV by laboratory confirmatory tests would be reclassified as confirmed cases (dotted line in [Figure 2](#)) and follow-up would occur as described in the case investigation algorithm. The data collection process may or may not be re-triggered in this instance, but would depend on the country resources and type of contact (for example, if the contact is a health worker, then a further investigation might be warranted to inform public health action).

Table 1: Summary of the data collection

Form number	Purpose of form	Collecting from whom?	When should it be collected?
CASES			
Form A1	Case <i>initial</i> report form	For confirmed cases	Day of recruitment into the HHTI investigation (as soon as possible after identification of a case) (Day 1)
Form A2	Case <i>follow-up</i> forms	For confirmed cases	14 days after completion of Form A1 (Day 14). Updates should be obtained regularly, if all the required information is not available at the time of completing this form.
CONTACTS			
Form B1	Contact <i>initial</i> reporting form	For household contacts of cases	Day of recruitment into the HHTI investigation (ideally within 24 hours after identification of the index case) (Day 1)
Form B2	Contact <i>follow-up</i> forms	For household contacts of cases	14 days after completion of Form B1 (Day 14)
CASES & CONTACTS			
Form C	Track and summarize all laboratory results (and methods used)	For confirmed cases and household contacts	This table will need to be filled/updated at each specimen collection time point above
Form D: Symptom diary	Record presence or absence of various signs or symptoms	For confirmed cases and household contacts	Between days 2 and 14 after administration of the initial questionnaire

Figure 2: case investigation algorithm and summary of data collection tools

4.6 Specimen collection and transport

The following is intended to guide specimen collection from confirmed cases and their close contacts in a household setting. Careful planning should be done to ensure arrangements are in place for who will collect the samples, how to access required PPE and how to arrange safe sample collection and transport of specimens. Sample collection and transport should follow national guidelines.

The types of respiratory specimen collected (i.e., nasal swabs, nasopharyngeal swab, throat swabs, saliva, sputum, and combinations of these) and the demonstrated sensitivity and specificity of each for detecting virus using RT-PCR or the laboratory method being recommended ([Appendix C](#))

How the specimens will be collected (professionally or self-collected). It may be possible for participants to self-collect respiratory specimens. This may reduce staffing burden/costs on study nurses or professional collection services and enable frequent sampling when required per the sampling strategy. For example, self-swabbing has been demonstrated to be a reliable method for influenza and SARS-CoV-2 testing (37), although this is dependent on pre-planning, logistics of transport and the quality of training provided to participants (37, 38).

4.6.1 Sampling strategy

A **mandatory respiratory tract specimen** (nasopharyngeal/oropharyngeal swab) is required from all participants on **day 1 – baseline**. This study visit should occur as soon as possible ideally within 24 hours after laboratory confirmation of the index case. The initial respiratory specimen aims to identify co-primary cases as well as subsequent cases as quickly as possible after they are infected, to minimise the risk of misclassification of participants.

Mandatory follow-up respiratory tract specimens (nasopharyngeal/oropharyngeal swab) are required from all participants on **days 2-7 based on their appearance of symptoms**. The study coordinator will make a telephonically call to household on daily basis and if the household contact gives a history of suggestive symptoms, household visit will be conducted to collect the respiratory sample of that particular household member.

4.6.2 Specimen collection and transport

Appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) should be worn when specimens are being collected from index cases and all contacts (37). All those involved in collecting and transporting specimens should be trained in the safe handling practices of infectious substances and infectious spill decontamination procedures. For details regarding the collection and transport of samples, please refer to the case management algorithm and laboratory guidance in the country, or to WHO laboratory guidance (40, 41).

For each biological sample collected, the time of collection, the conditions for transportation and the time of arrival at the laboratory should be recorded. Specimens should ideally be collected within 3 days of the onset of clinical symptoms and reach the laboratory as soon as possible after collection. If the specimen is not likely to reach the laboratory and processed within 48 hours, it should be frozen, preferably at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and shipped on dry ice as per WHO guidance (40). It is, however, important to aliquot each sample to avoid repeated freezing and thawing of specimens to avoid the deleterious effects of such handling on the infectivity of virus and the yield of viral RNA. The storage of respiratory and serum specimens in domestic frost-free freezers should be avoided, owing to their wide temperature fluctuations. Serum should be separated from whole blood and can be stored at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one week and shipped at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or frozen to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or lower and shipped on dry ice.

Transport of specimens within national borders should comply with applicable national regulations. International transport of specimens should follow applicable international regulations as described in the WHO Guidance on regulations for the transport of infectious substances 2021–2022 (42).

4.6.3 Diagnostic testing

PCR assay using gene Xpert system will be used for diagnostic testing of Influenza and Respiratory Syncytial Virus.

The PCR assay will be performed using Xpert Xpress Flu/RSV test cartridges that runs on the GeneXpert System.

The GeneXpert System is a cartridge-based molecular diagnostic platform that integrates sample processing (automates and integrates sample extraction), nucleic acid purification and amplification (using real-time PCR), and target sequence detection to provide rapid, accurate results for infectious diseases. The GeneXpert systems consist of an instrument, a personal computer, and preloaded software for running tests and viewing the results. Each test requires the use of a single-use disposable GeneXpert cartridge that contains target-specific reagents and carries out the RT-PCR and PCR processes. Because the cartridges are self-contained, the risk of cross-contamination between samples is minimized. The Xpert Xpress Flu/RSV test cartridges include reagents for the detection and differentiation of influenza A, influenza B, and RSV viral RNA directly from NP swabs and NS specimens from patients with signs and symptoms of respiratory tract infection. The primers and probes in the Xpert Xpress Flu/RSV test are designed to amplify and detect unique sequences in the genes that encode the following proteins: influenza A matrix (M), influenza A basic polymerase (PB2), influenza A acidic protein (PA), influenza B matrix (M), influenza B non-structural protein (NS), and the RSV A and RSV B nucleocapsid. A Sample Processing Control (SPC) and a Probe Check Control (PCC) are also included in the cartridge. The SPC is present to control for an adequate amplification process and to monitor for the presence of inhibitors in the PCR reaction. The PCC verifies reagent rehydration, PCR tube filling in the cartridge, probe integrity, and dye stability.

Specimens for testing: Nasal swab (NS) or nasopharyngeal swab (NPS) will be collected according to standard procedures, and placed into the Nasal Sample Collection Kit for Viruses (viral transport tubes containing 3 mL transport medium).

Sample Transport:

The labelled samples will be transported as per the WHO guidelines. Briefly, the samples will be subjected to triple Packaging and will be transferred to the lab in a temperature-regulated (2-8 degree C) box. In the laboratory, the samples will be stored at samples at 4°C(2-8°C) till they are tested. If there is a delay in testing beyond 72 hours, the sample will be stored below -70°C.

Diagnostic algorithm

Sensitivity and Specificity of test kits:

PPA (Positive Percent Agreement) and NPA (Negative Percent Agreement)-

94.6% and 99.4%, detection of influenza A;

100% and 99.2% for influenza B, respectively;

100% and 99.8%, for RSV, respectively

□ Analytical specificity- 100%

[Ref: Xpert® Xpress Flu/RSV kit insert/user manual](#)

4.7 Data management

4.7.1 Data sharing

The proposed Pilot phase study is a single-site study, which will be conducted in the field practice area of a medical college. Therefore, data management will be a single site under the supervision of the Principal Investigator and data sharing will be with WHO Country office and WHO SEARO Region.

For phase 2 study Data may be pooled and aggregated across multiple sites by WHO if the data are collected in a consistent manner, to increase analytic power and improve precision in estimates of severity and transmissibility. The pooling of this data will depend on how transmission dynamics vary between countries. If the data are shared by the implementing organization or country, with WHO or with any agency or institution providing support for data analysis, data shared will include only the investigation identification number and not any personally identifiable information. Any data sharing must also be covered by any ethical approvals, where relevant, or national regulations.

4.7.2 Reporting of findings

Any investigation of this nature should include reporting on the following information, stratified by age, sex and relevant time and place characteristics if sample size permits:

- the number of confirmed cases initially identified in the setting (symptomatic and asymptomatic);
- the number of closed settings, the number of contacts (close and other);
- the number of PCR-confirmed cases among contacts;
- the number of symptomatic contacts;
- the number of contacts with serologic evidence of infection, and;
- parameter estimates with uncertainty.

If sample size permits, these numbers should be stratified by age, sex or other relevant characteristics.

4.7.3 Study Variables

Dependent variables	Independent variables
Secondary infection rate	Age
Secondary clinical attack rate	Gender
Symptomatic: asymptomatic proportion	Education
House hold attack rate	Marital status
Number of secondary cases per index case	Religion
Severity of disease	Occupation
Infection: hospitalization ratio	Family size
Duration of illness	Overcrowding
Duration of viral shedding	Ventilation
Infection-fatality ratio	Air Pollution
Viral load	Cough antiquates
Healthcare utilization	Vaccination

5. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Approval of the local institutional ethics committee of Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, New Delhi, India, will be sought before conducting the study. From all the participants, written informed consent will be taken before the interview after explaining the objectives of the study in the local language (Hindi) (Annexure XX). Copies of the participant information form will be issued to them, and full written informed consent will be taken.

In the pilot phase laboratory database from HIMSR & HAHC data will be utilised for the index case recruitment, so no permission from the district will be required. Whereas, in phase 2 District IHIP database will be utilised, for which administrative permission from the district will be sought for extracting the routine data.

5.1 Informed consent and assent

The purpose of the investigation will be explained to all individuals willing to participate, before the start of the investigation in the local language (Hindi) (Annexure XX).

All eligible individuals, regardless of whether or not they are well or unwell should be able to participate in the investigation. For individuals who lack the decisional capacity to consent at the time of the investigation, consent/assent by proxy (parent/ guardian/ spouse/ family member) may be considered so as to not unduly exclude individuals from participating in the investigation.

An appropriately trained member of the investigation team will need to explain to each participant that participation in the investigation is voluntary and that he or she is free to withdraw, without justification, from the investigation at any time without consequences and without affecting professional responsibilities or educational rights. A member of the investigation must also be able to answer any questions any individual willing to participate in the investigation may have related to the procedures of the investigation.

The processes related to withdrawal of a participant need to be described both in the protocol and in the information given to the participant at the time of enrolment. In this description it must be made clear that a participant can withdraw from the investigation, without justification, at any time by informing one of the members of the investigation team. The contact details of one of the members of the investigation need to be provided in the information for the participant. If any participant decides to withdraw from the investigation, the samples collected and data should be discarded, except if the participant indicates that these can be kept for the purpose of conducting the investigation, or for future studies of other infectious pathogens

Participants or their parent/ guardian/ spouse will be informed about the test results, with an explanation of the interpretation and implications of the test results.

5.2 Risks and benefits for subjects

This investigation poses minimal risk to participants, involving the collection of a small amount of blood and respiratory specimens. The direct benefit to the participant is the possibility for early detection of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection, which would allow for appropriate monitoring and treatment for themselves and their close contacts. The primary benefit of the investigation is indirect, in that data collected will help improve and guide efforts to understand transmission of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV and potentially reduce or slow down further spread of the virus.

In terms of treatment of cases, case management will be facilitated by early detection of the disease and will follow national guidance, but the investigators may or may not be directly involved in clinical management of patients. Processes on how confirmed cases will be referred for medical care, as well as details on provisions of care as part of the investigation will need to be detailed. There will be no incentives while participating in this investigation, but participants will be provided relevant and updated health advice to reduce the risk of transmission and severe outcomes where possible.

5.3 Reporting of serious adverse events, including death of a participant

Any serious adverse event, including death, of a participant during the investigation period, needs to be immediately (within 24h) reported to the Principal Investigator and the institution responsible for the investigation. The contact details for reporting serious adverse events needs to be provided to each member of the investigation team. In accordance with national regulations, any serious adverse event, may also have to be reported to the local ethical review committee, if the adapted protocol was not deemed exempt from local ethical review committee.

5.4 Confidentiality

Participant confidentiality will be maintained throughout the investigation. All subjects who participate in the investigation will be assigned a unique identification number by the investigation team, for the labelling of questionnaires and clinical specimens. The link of this identification number to individuals will be maintained by the investigation team and the ministry of health (or equivalent) and will not be disclosed elsewhere. Data and specimens will be securely stored. If the data are shared by the implementing organization with WHO or any agency or institution providing support for data analysis, the shared data will include only the investigation identification number and not any personally identifiable information. Data sharing outside the country must be managed according to national laws and regulations, as appropriate.

Comment: The investigators will need to describe how data and specimens will be securely stored, the duration of storage and the destruction of data and specimens at the end of the duration of storage, in accordance with national laws and regulations.

According to the WHO surveillance standards for influenza, all patients have a right to privacy and confidentiality (49). Hence, all data that is gathered will be kept confidential except to the extent necessary to disclose or transmit it for public health purposes. Article 45 of the International Health Regulations (2005) (IHR) describes the "treatment of personal data" (50). Personally identifiable data collected under the IHR should be kept confidential and processed anonymously, as required by national law. However, such data may be disclosed for assessments and management of public health risks, provided the data are processed fairly and lawfully.

5.5 Future use of samples

The investigators may decide on potential future use of specimens and the time-frame for destruction of specimens and seek appropriate national approvals for this. If this is the case, the investigators will need to provide more specific information on potential future use of specimens and the time-frame for destruction of specimens, including in the information for the participant and the informed consent/assent form. Additional consent forms may need to be developed by the country, according to national laws and regulations, if the investigations calls for storage and future use of samples.

5.6 Prevention of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection among investigation personnel

All personnel involved in investigation visits must be trained in procedures for infection prevention and control (as determined by national or local guidelines) (51) when collecting data or specimens in proximity to confirmed cases and close contacts. These procedures should include proper hand hygiene and the correct use of surgical or respiratory face masks, to minimize their risk of infection. WHO technical guidance on infection prevention and control specific to influenza A, Influenza B and RSV can be found on the WHO website.

6. ANALYSIS PLAN

6.1 Sample size

The sample size of the investigation will be determined by the number of household contacts and assumptions made relating to the transmissibility of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV. Effort will be made to include all contacts, upto 5 household contacts of each index case, to improve the precision and reduce bias in parameter estimates.

Considering a secondary attack rate of 0.5 at the household level we assumed the prevalence of 50%. Considering 90% power and 95% confidence interval and applying Schwartz formula, the sample size came out to be 384, which was increased to 440, considering lost to follow up. Assuming average family size of four, we determined to include 110 index cases and their 330 households contacts for our study. If any household had more than 4 members, the inclusion of all members will done. Those not consenting to participate in the study were excluded.

Sample size for Pilot Study Phase

In the pilot phase, the sample size will be determined purposively rather than by statistical calculation. A total of five laboratory-confirmed index cases, along with up to five household contacts per index case, will be randomly recruited based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria

**For this phase of implementation and Pilot testing,
we plan to enroll**

- **5 index cases**
- **upto 5 household contacts of each index case.**

6.2 Plan of analysis

Household transmission investigations will be not be able to answer every question we have about influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection, but they will contribute key data in the early stages of an epidemic, which can inform public health interventions. Other protocols for investigations for influenza A, Influenza B and RSV can assist in providing supplementary data to improve estimates of key epidemiological parameters. For the proposed study unit of analysis will be an individual within households.

Prior to commencing the investigation, an analysis plan should be developed incorporating the study objectives, definitions and planned analysis to address each objective. Pre-specifying the analysis plan will help to ensure that all relevant data are being collected. Please refer to the WHO Statistical Analysis Plan as part of the supporting Toolkit.

A descriptive analysis (time, place, person) of the closed setting transmission investigation should provide an insight into the clinical spectrum and course of disease due to influenza A, Influenza B and RSV infection from individual cases - for example, the number of close contacts with symptomatic or asymptomatic confirmed infection, by age and underlying risk factors. See Figure 5

A statistical analysis (epidemiological parameters estimation) of the closed setting data will provide estimates of the transmissibility and severity of influenza A, Influenza B and RSV for example, the secondary attack rate or hospitalization/fatality rate by setting, age and other risk factors.

Data collected will be entered, compiled, analyzed, and statistically tested using appropriate statistical tests. Relevant mean, proportions, ratios, secondary attack rates will be calculated as per study variables. Analysis of the data will be done using SPSS 26.0 (SPSS Inc., USA) software.

Limitation:

This study being a case-ascertained study, index cases will be recruited from a laboratory-confirmed database of a tertiary care hospital, where predominantly moderate-to-severe cases are reported. This recruitment

strategy may introduce bias, limiting the generalizability of findings and potentially underestimating the secondary attack rate compared to community-based recruitment.